

OPINIONS OF EASTERN THINKERS ABOUT TEACHER RELATIONSHIPS

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the importance of teachers' communication culture, speech competence, and linguistic richness in modern education. Based on the ideas of Eastern thinkers such as al-Farabi, Yusuf Khas Hajib, Alisher Navoi, and Zahiriddin Babur, the article explains the ethical, educational, and aesthetic role of speech in pedagogy. It also examines A.S. Makarenko's methods of pedagogical communication, key communicative tasks, and the teacher's professional responsibility in managing interaction. The article concludes that communication culture, eloquence, public speaking, and linguistic richness are fundamental indicators of teachers' professional excellence.*

Keywords. *Pedagogical communication, speech culture, communicative competence, Eastern thinkers, rhetoric, A.S. Makarenko, teaching mastery, linguistic richness.*

Social processes taking place in the world in recent years force us to choose new ways of development and form a new context in various spheres of human activity, including science and education, where it is important to lay a solid foundation for successful education even in the early stages of education.

From the first days of life, a person needs communication with others. This need is constantly and constantly developing. Therefore, this situation determines that continuous communication is a necessary condition of life. Communication is a complex, multifaceted activity, which can be formed through specific knowledge and skills that need to be mastered, as well as through accumulated social experience. The key to successful adaptation is a high level of communication. The success of education in our modern life is aimed at the formation of a comprehensively developed personality, his ability to work and live in a constantly changing world, as well as a constant search for innovative forms and methods of teaching.

In this regard, the words of our President Sh. Mirziyoyev, "We will mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society so that our youth can develop and be happy, independent thinkers, possessing high intellectual and spiritual potential, who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale," directly correspond to the purpose of our work. The great thinkers of the Near and Middle East (Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Yusuf al-Kindi, Nasir

Khusraw, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Omar Khayyam, Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi and others) and many enlightened scientists have emphasized the importance of the role of the teacher in educating the growing generation, especially the importance of the educator's communication with the student. The essence, methods, forms, tools and principles of communication have been developed by scholars, and they have not lost their relevance even today. In particular, the issues of goodness, etiquette, and politeness are summarized in one volume of Imam Bukhari's 4-volume work "Al-Jame' as-Sahih" in the hadiths about etiquette, morality, behavior, and communication. This book lists three conditions for the perfection of faith: having the right faith; having good relations with people; working on oneself and calling oneself to worship and obedience. Faith is likened to a tree and has more than 60 branches, - the signs of faith are listed, each of which is a quality that affects the perfection of a person's spiritual image. Interactive technologies are gaining the greatest popularity. They are based on our own search for knowledge, as a result of which personal development occurs. The use of interactive methods forms independent and logical thinking in students and develops the skills to quickly and long-term remember new things.

If primary school students do not develop good speech, they will not be able to convey their knowledge to children, no matter how perfect it is. Therefore, their constant practice and mastery of various forms of communication remain one of the urgent problems of today.

Despite the large number of interactive methods today, we can see that their level of application is still low. Therefore, we need to develop the skills of teachers to use them in the classroom.

The study of the basic principles of communication and its main features, as a rule, the relationship between such concepts as the culture of society and the culture of man, was carried out by M.S. Kagan, S.A. Arutyunov, V.M. Mejuyev, E.N. Yurkevich and others. The problems of the culture of interpersonal communication were considered by G.N. Andreeva, L.P. Gadzayova, I.I. Zaretskaya, E.P. Ilyin, S.L. Rubinstein and others.

A.A. Bodalev, O.I. Danilenko, V.A. Kan-Kalik, A.A. Leontyev, N.V. Kuzmina and N.E. Shchurkova in their studies proved the need for teachers to take a humane position in relation to learners and to be able to fulfill their professional duties through properly formed communication, and the need for targeted development of their communicative competence in the future. Also, from Russian educators: M.E. Bershansky, V.V. Guzeev, L.I. Denisovich, E.F. Zeer, I.A. Winter, T.E. Isaeva, O.M. Karpenko, G.M. Kozhaspirova, O.E. Lebedev, O.I. Lukyanenko, K.G. Mitrofanov, G.K. Selevko, I.I. Seregina, O.V. Sokolova, A.V. Khutorskoy, and V.A. Yakunin, in their research, analyze the concept of "competence" and consider the essence of a competency-based approach to education. In Russian pedagogy, V.A. Adolf, T.E.

Isaeva, N.B. Krylova, I.A. Kolesnikova, N.V. Kuzmina, A.K. Markova, L.M. Mitina, A.I. Mishchenko, E.M. Pavlyutenkov and V.A. Slastenin in their works on professional and pedagogical competence, N.N. Bogomolova, Yu.N. Emelyanov, I.A.Zimnyaya, M.I.Lukyanova, L.M.Mitina, L.A.Petrovskaya, A.V.Rastyannikov, E.I.Rogov and I.I.Rydanova discussed the issues of developing communicative competence of the future teacher, L.K. Geikhman, I.I.Zaretskaya, E.E.Kosilo, I.I.Rydanova, N.V.Kuzmina, J.Raven and L.M. Mitinalar revealing the structure of communicative competence gave, Yu.N.Emelyanov, D.A.Ivanov, S.V.Krivtsova, N.V.Kuzmina, A.K.Markova sources of developing communicative competence E.B.Bystray, V.G.Kostomarov, A.N.Leontiev, T.I.Lukyanenko and A.V.Mudrik studied the problem of forming communicative skills in future teachers in the educational process. We can see that the definition of communicative competence is closely related to understanding the essence of pedagogical communication in theoretical studies conducted by Russian scientists B.G. Ananiev, G.M. Andreeva, A.A. Bodalev, V.A. Goryanina, B.C. Grekhnev, M.S. Kogan, V.A. Kan-Kalik, Ya.L. Kolominsky, S.V. Kondratieva, A.A. Leontiev, A.V. Mudrik, B.D. Parygin, and Z.S. Smelkova.

A.S. Makarenko used various methods of influence through communication in his pedagogical experience. The methods used by him, in most cases, are based on a clear definition of the educational task and the correct organization of the situation on the basis of mutual communication with students. Sometimes this manifests itself in the form of “face-to-face influence”, while in some cases the student has the opportunity to understand the teacher’s signal even in the absence of direct verbal communication. Class meetings, formal conversations, and group events are important forms of direct and indirect communication with students. They serve as an important factor in understanding and revealing the personal potential of each student.

In Makarenko’s educational methods, group and individual conversations play a special role. However, the effectiveness of these methods is closely related to the situation and form in which they are used. Therefore, the analysis of how the communication process proceeds in different situations and the selection of methods of pedagogical influence in accordance with the situation are one of the criteria that determine the professional skills of a teacher.

The effective performance of communicative tasks by a teacher is, first of all, inextricably linked with the specific forms of pedagogical activity, the stage of formation of the class team, the degree of adherence to the principles of communication management, the age and individual characteristics of students, as well as the methods chosen for implementing pedagogical influence. A clear definition of communicative tasks in the communication process and the

correct coordination of the ratio between them and the methodology of pedagogical influence are one of the main factors ensuring the high effectiveness of pedagogical interaction.

In this regard, a two-way connection is noticeable: firstly, the methodology used in working with the class team is implemented directly through the communication system; Secondly, the communication process itself is based on the strategic approaches of the selected educational and educational impact methodology. Future teachers master the basics of professional and pedagogical communication in higher pedagogical educational institutions, and also strengthen them during their practical work and in the process of professional self-formation.

It can be said that in pedagogical activity, the culture of communication, the richness of the language, eloquence, politeness, and the art of oratory are not only a means of communication, but also the most important criteria that determine the effectiveness of education. Their mutual harmony is an expression of the cultural wealth and professional maturity of the teacher.

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